

Journeys into third space working

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In our recent article (Vere et al., 2024), we explored third space working in universities drawing on our three doctoral research projects. We reflected on individual, institutional and sector-wide experiences of third space working and how boundaries between academic and professional staff can be crossed and even dismantled to enable more productive relationships and working.

Part One: Journeys into third space working: personal experiences of boundary-crossing

An asynchronous interaction with Padlet materials in Week One of the Slowposium

To begin with, we shared our three distinct, yet connected, experiences of third space professionals working in HE in England through three mini case studies and/or vlogs, accessible to participants in a Padlet, illustrated below.

Material for Journeys into third space, available online at <https://uonarts.padlet.org/afztw/materials-for-journeys-into-third-space-webster-deakin-verne-wwj8sp8bd9a3qfq9>

We posed three questions to the Slowposium participants as follows:

1. What boundaries do you cross in your current role or have you crossed during your career?
2. What boundaries do you feel unable to cross, and why?

3. How can we create spaces in HE in which we can cross or dismantle boundaries?

Part Two: How can we facilitate third space working within our organisations?

A live online session in Week Two of the Slowposium

Drawing again on Vere et al. (2024), we hosted a live online discussion/webinar focusing on the questions provoked by the article.

During the discussion/webinar, we linked to challenges and opportunities shared by participants in Week One and engaged live participants in unpicking some of the gnarlier issues of working in the third space.

Reference

Vere, K., Verney, C., & Webster-Deakin, T. (2024). Crossing and dismantling boundaries: recognising the value of professional staff within higher education. *London Review of Education*, 22.1.29. <https://doi.org/10.14324/LRE.22.1.29>

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